

AVAILMENT AND ENHANCEMENT OF BENEFITS FOR SENIOR CITIZENS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF ALFONSO, CAVITE

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ABSTRACT

As the elderly population grows, related concerns and challenges become more prevalent and require attention. Ensuring their well-being involves recognizing their contributions and addressing their unique challenges. This study determines the availment and enhancement of benefits for senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite. It evaluated how the respondents avail services like medicine and drug purchases, medical and dental services, and essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment. Also, the possible enhancement of concerned agencies on the benefits accrued to senior citizens, particularly hospitals and clinics, groceries, and drugstores. One hundred fifty senior citizens, one hundred fifty guardians of the senior citizens, and five personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of Alfonso, Cavite were identified as respondents using purposive-criterion sampling. To achieve the research objectives, this study employed a quantitative research approach. A sample survey utilizing self-constructed questionnaires was used to collect primary data, while secondary data were gathered from various relevant sources. The findings indicate that senior citizens are satisfied with the benefits and services provided. This general approval underscores the strengths of the current support system for the elderly. However, the study concludes that, despite this satisfaction, an information campaign is essential to effectively disseminate details about the plans, activities, and services available to them. This will ensure that senior citizens are fully informed and can make the best use of the available resources for them.

Keywords: *basic services, benefits and privileges, social inclusion, welfare, social support systems, quantitative research*

INTRODUCTION

In our society, the senior citizens are respected and important members of the society. They stand for the values and rich cultural heritage of the Philippines since they uphold and form the development of the community; they are the cornerstones of resilience, life, and knowledge. This archipelago nation values its senior citizens greatly for their contributions to family, community, and nation-building. People call them "Lolo" or "Lola" (grandfather or grandma). Despite their traditional duties, senior citizens in the Philippines face new opportunities and difficulties in a rapidly evolving social and economic landscape. This introduction determines the many aspects of senior citizenship, such as their roles, rights, and problem encounter, with the goal of addressing and understanding senior citizens in the Philippines and connecting to the provision of the law under Republic Act No. 9994, otherwise known as the expanded senior citizen act of 2010.

In the 1987 Philippine Constitution, it gives assurance and provides the welfare and rights of the nation's elderly population. The preservation and advancement of the interests of the elderly are directly addressed by several provisions in the constitution. The Constitution states a strong emphasis on advancing social justice throughout all stages of the country's development, as stated in Article II, section 11 emphasizes on how important it is for the government to see to it the needs of vulnerable groups—including senior citizens. It establishes laws and initiatives meant to improve and develop the socioeconomic standing of elder Filipinos. The state must implement an integrated and comprehensive strategy for health development, guaranteeing the availability and accessibility of health services, as required by Article XIII, Section 11 of the said Constitution.

Moreover, in the Philippines, Republic Act No. 9994 is the focus of the study since it serves as an essential tool for addressing the elderly persons regarding their rights, welfare, and social inclusion. The law ensures that elderly people can age with dignity, respect, and support by offering financial help, healthcare access, discounts, other advantages, and privileges. It also recognizes the vital contributions that elderly people make to society. This law plays a pivotal role in improving the welfare and quality of life of senior citizens in the Philippines.

In this study, the researcher focused on the municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, as the locale of the study. It is one of the most civilized municipalities in the province and is considered a first-class municipality in Cavite, with a total of thirty-two (32) barangays and a total population of 6,438 senior citizens compared with neighboring municipalities with smaller populations, such as Indang, Mendez, and Maragondon, Cavite.

The sector of senior citizens, which consists of individuals aged 60 and above and is experiencing rapid growth on a global scale, represents a captivating and multifaceted area that is ripe for exploration and study within the academic community. Within this cognitive realm, a multitude of urgent matters emerge, spanning a diverse array of

subjects including bodily wellness, psychological health, interpersonal interactions, economic security, and the attainment of technological competencies.

Despite the numerous issues confronting older individuals, it is imperative to acknowledge and appreciate the vital function they serve as essential constituents of the community, offering substantial input across a multitude of spheres. One of the most notable ways in which senior citizens enrich the community is through the vast repository of wisdom and expertise that they offer, serving as mentors and guides to younger generations across diverse fields of knowledge and practice. Leveraging their wealth of life experiences and learned insights, senior citizens provide a unique perspective that is of immeasurable value in the process of making collective decisions within the community, infusing deliberations with deep historical awareness and a forward-looking vision for long-term sustainability and growth.

Additionally, this sector plays a significant role in the vitality and comprehensive development of a community, serving as a vital link between different age groups, facilitating the exchange of ideas, values, and traditions. Moreover, they actively work towards strengthening social bonds, fostering a sense of unity and cooperation among the community members. It is imperative to acknowledge the significance of their presence and to actively encourage their ongoing engagement to establish a resilient and harmonious society.

In the Philippines, this sector encounters many challenges that have a significant impact on their overall welfare and standard of living. One of the foremost concerns that confronts the older demographic in this nation is the issue of accessibility to healthcare services. This pertinent matter poses a considerable obstacle for numerous senior citizens who are seeking cost-effective and top-tier medical care, particularly in remote and underserved areas characterized by a scarcity or even an absence of healthcare facilities. Next, it is a serious issue that older people in the Philippines have restricted access to healthcare. For elder Filipinos, the Expanded Senior Citizens Act of 2010 (Republic Act No. 9994) presents serious obstacles due to its ineffective implementation. Notwithstanding the provisions of the law intended to enhance the welfare and well-being of elderly residents, several problems, including a lack of awareness and understanding, led to the unsatisfactory implementation of RA 9994.

Provincial Board Member Valeriano S. Encabo introduced and sponsored Provincial Ordinance No. 235, also known as the "Free Parking Ordinance for Senior Citizens and Persons with Disabilities," in the Province of Cavite. The ordinance that took effect in 2019 exempts all senior citizens (SCs) and persons with disabilities (PWDs) from paying parking fees typically charged by business establishments within the province. The provincial legislation exempts senior citizens (SCs) and persons with disabilities (PWDs) from paying parking fees in malls, business establishments, and private hospitals within Cavite province. To avail of this benefit, individuals must either be the driver or a passenger of the private vehicle and present SC/PWD cards upon entry to the parking area. This exemption does not apply to overnight parking. Additionally, the legislation

excludes public utility vehicles (PUVs) such as public utility jeepneys (PUJs), tricycles, buses, taxis, and similar vehicles.

In conclusion, this study discusses the realities regarding the availability and enhancement of benefits for senior citizens in the different areas of services. Also, it addresses what healthcare access, financial assistance, social welfare, and benefits and privileges senior citizens need to address. The study displayed a descriptive feature; as such, its primary aim was to address the availment to the services among elderly individuals regarding the law and its enforcement in the specified regions. Through this evaluation, an insight into the current degree of law enforcement was presented. In its entirety, this analysis contributes to the enhancement of law enforcement at the community level, the efficacy of municipal operations, the formulation of policies, and the execution of programs at the community level, in addition to the societal standing of elderly citizens.

Theoretical Framework

In the Philippines, individuals who have attained the age of 60 will be duly recognized and designated as senior citizens in accordance with the established legal framework, specifically the Expanded Senior Citizen Act of 2010. At this moment in their lives, these elderly individuals are entitled to benefits and privileges that have been specified under the law. The overarching objective behind the provision of such support is to enhance and optimize the welfare and contribution of these esteemed elders towards the overarching goal of nation-building and societal development.

The theoretical framework employed in this study was the New Public Management (NPM). In 1991, new public management was introduced by Hood and Jackson, scholars from the United Kingdom and Australia. Christopher In an article he published in 1991, Hood was the original proponent of the term New Public Management.

This theory emphasizes efficiency, effectiveness, and customer orientation in public administration. Citizen charters are a direct application of these principles, treating citizens as 'customers' of public services. The citizen's charter serves as an instrument by the government utilized by an institution to enhance its services based on the demands and expectations of its service recipients. It provides a guide for the services offered by the specific offices and institutions to meet the needs of the public, the procedures and processes for delivering public services, the mechanisms for addressing grievances in instances of service failure, and the responsibilities of citizens in receiving the service (Sharma and Agnihotri, 2001).

The term "new public management" is becoming a little old. It was always a challenging and far from consistent collection of ideas, and from the moment the development was initially viewed, it was widely criticized as a helpful standard that emerging countries should follow. The contradictory mix of ideas and concerns surrounding NPM consideration in the 1980s and early 1990s led to a deeper caution regarding its broad use in the late 1990s. Maybe uncertainty has now been established.

The claim that there is little in the NPM procedural combination appropriate for the politicized public sectors in many developing nations is undoubtedly recognizable to tired professionals and personnel of development organizations (Manning, 2001).

Through the exploration of this theory, an in-depth analysis is conducted on the defining features of the paradigm of public administration. This model is conceptualized as an entity that operates within the confines of political oversight, thereby emphasizing the importance of being subject to the direction and supervision of political authorities.

Furthermore, it is characterized by a rigidly structured bureaucratic system that adheres strictly to a hierarchical organizational arrangement. Such institutional dynamics are observed within the administrative framework of the Municipality of Alfonso, situated in the province of Cavite. Since the Citizen's Charter was developed within the framework of New Public Management (NPM) and serves as a tool for ensuring the accountability of service providers, the researcher examined how the Citizen's Charter was formulated and implemented by the Municipal Government of Alfonso's Office of Senior Citizen Affairs, and how it addressed the availability and enhancement of benefits for senior citizens.

Conceptual Framework

To guide the flow and give a visual representation of the variables in this study, the researcher used the input, process, and output (IPO) model to show the availability and enhancement of benefits for senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite. The input-process-Output (IPO) model is a fundamental concept in systems analysis and software development. It provides a structured approach to understanding and describing how a system or process works. Essentially, it breaks down a system into three key components: the input, which is the data or information that is fed into the system; the process, which is the actions or operations performed on the input data; and the output, which is the results or information generated by the process.

This conceptual framework is put in place as a guide and model to illustrate how the variables were treated in the study. The figure showed how the researcher conducted the study and how they attained the necessary information required by the study. It also discussed how the study flowed throughout the entire span of time given.

The figure presented below is the researchers portrayed framework of the study:

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

It illustrates the descriptive study's formulated research paradigm. The purpose and agenda of the study. The first box, input, consists of the primary statements that the researchers assumed to find out in this study, which include the following: discovering the demographic background of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, and length of residency; determining the availment of the respondents in the services provided by the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, particularly the medicine and dental services; medical and dental services; essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment; and the possible enhancement of benefits for them in the various agencies within the jurisdiction of the municipality, such as hospitals, clinics, groceries, and drugstores.

Meanwhile, identifying the profile of the respondents is necessary since it ensures the validity and accuracy of the study by finding the most qualified respondents. Also, determining the availability of the services is an important area of the study since that is the foundation for finding the areas that respondents weaken or strengthen. Then, looking for the possible enhancement of benefits for the senior citizens is necessary since the implementation of the law is the most necessary part that provides the area that needs to focus on drafting an information drive that focuses on educating senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, about the services and benefits available to them.

Additionally, the second box is the process, served as the procedures, wherein a profiling questionnaire is administered in person to ensure that legitimate, qualified respondents participate in the study and by using appropriate statistical treatment of data.

Lastly, output is the last box, which shows the expected outcome or recommendation based on the findings of this study.

In conclusion, the framework comprises recommendations aimed at establishing an information campaign to improve the well-being of elderly residents in Alfonso, Cavite. These recommendations could entail policy modifications, interventions, or support structures designed to expand opportunities, accessibility, social support, and healthcare services for the beneficiaries of the law within the municipality. Furthermore, it assists in devising an action strategy to bolster the execution of RA 9994, and local mandates and tackle the difficulties and issues experienced by senior citizens in study.

Research Questions

This study determines the availment and enhancement of benefits for senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions.

1. What is the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. length of residency?
2. How do the respondents avail themselves of the following services provided by the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite:
 - 2.1. medicine and drug purchases;
 - 2.2. medical and dental services; and
 - 2.3. essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment?
3. What are the possible enhancements to benefits for respondents among the various agencies in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, such as:
 - 3.1. hospitals and clinics;
 - 3.2. groceries; and
 - 3.3. drugstores?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their availment of services?
5. Is there a significant difference between the responses of the respondents when grouped accordingly?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what is the recommended information campaign that focuses on educating senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, about the services and benefits available to them?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter contained the research design that deals with the well-informed design, population and sampling refers to the set of individuals participated in the study and the process of statistical analysis where the researcher use to determine the population, respondents of the study that discuss the individuals involved in the study,

research instrument that discuss the too use to collect data, validation of the instrument that assure the intended to measure the validity, data gathering procedure that deals on the gathering of data, data analysis with a process of analyzing and interpreting data, and ethical considerations that assures the principle of voluntary participation.

Research Design

The study contains the features of a quantitative research approach that ensures a systematic and rigorous investigation to support the findings obtained from the data collection. Quantitative research involves the collection of numerical data that describes and expounds the data that is subjected to statistical analysis. It has control over extraneous variables to establish causal relationships (Creswell, 2014, p. 5). Another aspect of this method is determining the significance of the study design. Quantitative research involves gathering data through surveys, experiments, observations that are quantified, and other means that deal with numbers, statistics, and expressions conveyed in numbers and graphs. It is necessary to acquire a variety of types of knowledge (Streefkerk, 2021).

The quantitative data that was gathered by the researcher was used to determine how the respondents avail themselves of the services provided by the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, particularly medicine and drug purchases, medical and dental services, and essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment. Also, the possible enhancements to benefits for respondents among the various agencies such as hospitals, clinics, groceries, and drugstores. The research findings serve as a guide for establishing a recommended information drive that focuses on educating senior citizens. It also provides recommendations and suggestions for the development of senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite.

In addition, this study is correlational comparative in nature. It involves, without changing the variables, descriptive correlational research that examines and explains the correlations between variables and compares the responses of different groups of respondents. By using statistical analysis to find patterns between variables, it seeks to bring insight into the nature and extent of connections that exist within a specific group or population. The technique prepares the basis for further analysis and hypothesis testing by offering insightful information on the correlations between variables in specific circumstances (Creswell, 2014, p. 152).

In general, it is first intended to correlate the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their availment of services, and secondly, it is intended to compare the significant difference between the responses of the respondents when they are grouped. Therefore, by interpreting the numerical data with the use of statistical treatment, particularly Pearson r and ANOVA, the researcher was able to provide a relevant result that helped explain the objective of the study on addressing the concerns of senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite.

Sampling Technique

The research employed the Purposive-Criterion Sampling Technique, which involves a meticulous selection of participants from a set of eligible individuals based on careful judgment and consideration. It is used in research to select a specific group of individuals or units that may respond to or participate in any studied interest. This allowed the study to choose participants on purpose and not randomly; hence, it considered the presence of certain characteristics that meet the criteria, as well as the object and purpose of the study.

In addition, in a seminal work by Patton in his 2002 article entitled *Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods*, he stated that purposive sampling helps the researchers aim to gather in-depth insights from individuals who possess specific knowledge or experiences pertinent to the study's goals. It is also unique to other sampling techniques since it involves selecting participants based on specific characteristics.

Furthermore, a purposive criterion sampling technique was applied to understand the responses of the three categories of respondents, particularly the senior citizens and their guardians and personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens (OSCA). Also, this technique was utilized due to its accessibility and suitability for the study's objectives. The purpose of having a standard qualification for the participants was to easily identify the people who are primarily involved and have enough knowledge of the scope of this study.

Respondents of the Study

As of February 18, 2023, the city population (2023) provides that Alfonso, Cavite has a total of 6,438 senior citizens. In the age bracket of 60–69 years old, there are 3,832 with 1,771 male and 2,061 female, while for 70–79 years old, there are 1,864 with 747 male and 1,117 female, and for 80+ years, there are 742 with 221 male and 521 female. Majority of the senior citizens in the municipality is female with 3,699 population while the male is 2,739.

Table 1. *Age Distribution of Senior Citizens in Alfonso, Cavite*

Age Brackets	Male	Female	Total Population
60-69 years old	1,771	2,061	3,832
70-79 years old	747	1,117	1,864
80+ years old	221	521	742
Total	2,739	3,699	6,438

Since the 2023 data from the city population is given, the above table 1 serves as the basis for this study. Regardless of gender, the respondents were selected based on the set criteria for choosing, without any bias. To guarantee that the resulting sample is representative of the population, the researcher selected a sample based on the specific criteria given.

The respondents of the study were divided into three categories, composed of senior citizens and their guardians and personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens (OSCA). The researcher considered senior citizens to be one of the most important sectors in the community. There are many key roles that they participate in, like their political participation, in which they actively engage in the political process by voting, campaigning for candidates, and participating in grassroots political movements. Also, they play a vital role in preserving and passing down traditional Filipino customs, values, and practices to younger generations. Also, it is considering the view of the senior citizen guardians since they are the ones who are responsible for the respondent's care, and personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens (OSCA) since they are the office in each local government unit who safeguard the welfare of senior citizens and enhance capability with full benefits and protection.

Furthermore, in the process of determining the population of the participants, the researcher collaborates with the Office of the Senior Citizens (OSCA) and the Senior Citizens Organization in each barangay, while also coordinating with the Local Government Unit of Alfonso, Cavite, to ensure accuracy and thoroughness in data collection. The study's respondents have been selected based on these criteria: for the senior citizens, here's the following consideration: (1) must be at least 5 years reside in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite; (2) avail basic services for senior citizens; and (3) were able to participate in the study. For the guardian of the senior citizens, here are the following considerations: (1) must be a resident of the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite; (2) must be a relative of the respondent; and (3) must take care of the respondents; and for the personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens (OSCA), the only basis for them is that they are employees under this office regardless of employment status.

In addressing the exact number of respondents necessary for this study, one of the critical parts of the research process is figuring out how many respondents are appropriate for a large-scale quantitative study with an unknown population since, at the beginning, determining the exact number of senior citizens with guardians in the municipality has no data as presented in the Office of the Senior Citizens (OSCA). This critical stage in the research process demands careful thought and attention to various factors that can influence the outcome. Given the complex nature of the research problems, there are certain concepts to take into consideration, and the specific goals will determine the appropriate sample size. While these are general guidelines, it's essential to conduct a power analysis for a more precise sample size determination. This study is considered a large-scale study since it covers the entire Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, and requires an ideal sample size of 300 or more, which might be necessary for complex research questions or when high precision is required. A sample size of 300 or more should be justified based on specific research parameters and a power analysis since the sample size was determined based on the recommendations of Krejcie and Morgan (1970).

In this study, the researcher decided to set the total respondents at three hundred twenty-five (305), which are properly divided into three groups. The table below presents the distribution of respondents according to groups.

Table 2. *Respondents of the study*

Respondents	Sample Size	Percent
Senior Citizens	150	49.2
Guardian of the Senior Citizens	150	49.2
Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) Personnels	5	1.6
Total	305	100

The senior citizens and their guardians are from the above-mentioned thirty-two (32) barangays, namely: Amuyong, Barangay I, Barangay II, Barangay III, Barangay IV, Barangay V, Bilog, Buck Estate, Esperanza Ibaba, Esperanza Ilaya, Kaysuyo, Kaytitinga I, Kaytitinga II, Kaytitinga III, Luksuhin, Luksuhin Ilaya, Mangas I, Mangas II, Marahan I, Marahan II, Matagbak I, Matagbak II, Pajo, Palumlum, Santa Teresa, Sicat, Sinaliw Malaki, Sinaliw na Munti, Sulsugin, Taywanak Ibaba, Taywanak Ilaya, and Upli.

Research Instrument

The researcher first presented a consent form to the respondents and let them ensure that they willingly participated in the study and had allowed the researcher to use the data from the research instrument for the purposes stated in this study. The researcher also explained the instructions and contents of the questionnaire and asked permission from them to use the data that they provided before proceeding to the data gathering proper, which lasted for ten (10) minutes to fifteen (15) minutes per respondent.

For the purposes of this study, these are the following scoring and interpretation of the test:

Table 3. *Scoring and Interpretation of the test*

Point Scale	Range	Interpretation	Description
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Completely and wholeheartedly agree with a statement. It represents the highest level of agreement.
3	2.50- 3.24	Agree	Indicates a positive response to a statement, but with less intensity than strongly agree.
2	1.75- 2.49	Disagree	Signifying a negative response to a statement, it

			demonstrates a level of disagreement that is less forceful than strongly disagreeing.
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Most extreme negative response. It indicates a complete and total disagreement with the statement. There is no ambiguity or reservation in this response.

Specifically, the research instrument was composed of three (3) parts:

The first part (Part I) of the questionnaire was intended to elicit basic information, which identifies the demographic profile of participants from Alfonso, Cavite, with the considered preferences in terms of age, sex, and years of residency.

The second part (Part II) of the questionnaire contained a statement on a scale of 1–4, designed to be answered and elicit responses from the participants. It finds out how the respondents avail themselves of different services provided by the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, as mentioned in Chapter 1 of this study.

The third part of the questionnaire contained a statement with a scale of 1–4, like the second part, designed to be answered and elicit responses from the participants. It finds that the set of questions focused on the possible enhancements to benefits for senior citizens among various agencies in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, such as hospitals and clinics, groceries, and drugstores.

Validation of Instrument

The researcher uses the self-made survey questionnaire, it is subject to context validity and reliability. The self-made questionnaire was validated by the expert during the study and the content validity and reliability was validated and certified by the statistician.

Moreover, the researcher seeks the assistance of the Office of Senior Citizen Affairs in Alfonso, Cavite (OSCA), primarily the office head, by guiding the researcher in checking and validating the research instrument. There is also a full-time faculty member in Political Science at Cavite State University, Don Severino De las Alas Campus, who validates the research instrument since the chosen faculty are experts in the field of public administration.

The following table describes how different values of Cronbach's Alpha are usually interpreted:

Tables 4. Cronbach's Alpha Test of Validity Results

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

Based on the above different values of Cronbach's alpha, the alpha coefficients for all variables are accurate through careful examination and have been substantially proven. It revealed that the overall result of Cronbach's alpha for the reliability analysis of all the items for the are "EXCELLENT." This means that the instrument can be granted to the actual survey and no item needs to be removed. The result was attached in the appendices of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The study used both primary and secondary sources of data. For the primary sources, the researcher obtains information from books, online articles, journals, research studies, and some other relevant resources that helped the researcher to support the research study that is discussed in the review of related literature and studies.

On the other hand, the researcher utilized the survey method through a self-made survey questionnaire in which it collected data on discussing the research purpose in relation to the RA 9994. It basically contains a set of structured statements formulated by the researcher. For further examination, the content of the survey questionnaire was consulted to the experts for comments and potential recommendations for validity and reliability.

Furthermore, the researcher sought permission from Honorable Mayor Randy Salamat, Municipal Mayor of Alfonso, Cavite to conduct the study within the municipality and ask assistance from the Office of Senior Citizen Affairs (OSCA) and respective Senior Citizens President per barangay. It is also personally administered the explained mechanics and procedure in answering the survey questionnaire. The data gathering was subject to such limitations as provided in the ethical considerations.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researcher analyzes the data using appropriate statistical tools to determine the availability and enhancement of benefits for senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite. Given the study's quantitative approach, the collected data by the researchers was treated fairly and correctly using statistics. The organization, analysis, and interpretation were entirely based on numbers. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in the treatment of the data. After collecting data, the results

were tabulated, statistically analyzed according to the objectives, interpreted, and presented in tables with brief explanations for optimal clarity.

1. Cronbach's Alpha

A way to measure the internal consistency of a questionnaire or survey. Cronbach's Alpha ranges between 0 and 1, with higher values indicating that the survey or questionnaire is more reliable.

2. Descriptive Statistics

This analysis was used to describe and calculate numerical data. Here's the following measure of central tendency:

- Percentage is the proportion of a specific category or value within a dataset expressed as a fraction of 100 (Newbold et al. 2019).
- Frequency is the number of times a particular value or category occurs in a dataset (Newbold et al. 2019).
- Mean is the average of a data set
- Mode is involved to determine the most frequent value occurring in the responses of the sample.
- Standard Deviation is a statistical measurement of the amount of variation or dispersion of a set of values. It tells you how much your data points deviate from the average (mean).

3. Correlation Analysis

Kendall's tau-b (τ_b) was used to determine the significant relationship between the level of implementation of poverty alleviation programs and the level of implications on the informal waste pickers.

Formula: $\tau_b = (C - D / C + D)$

Where: C = the number of concordant pairs
D = the number of discordant pairs

4. ANOVA

To compare study findings from three or more unrelated samples or groups, a test is utilized. used to compare mean variations between more than two groups. It performs this by examining the variance of the data of the data and its distribution (hence the name). ANOVA specifically contrasts the degree of variance within groups with that between groups (Edanz, n.d)

Specifically, in interpreting the result, the Friedman test used, it is a non-parametric alternative to repeated measures ANOVA. It's used when the data is not normally distributed, or the assumptions of ANOVA are not met.

5. Computer Software

It is a data management and analysis that has featured modules for Jamovi Statistical Software, a free, open-source statistical software that has gained popularity

due to its user-friendly interface and powerful capabilities. It's designed to be accessible to both beginners and experienced researchers.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the interpretation of the data and results generated from the 305 respondents, which were properly divided into three groups, specifically one hundred fifty (150) senior citizens, one hundred fifty (150) guardians of the senior citizens, and five (5) personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of Alfonso, Cavite. The findings of the study are discussed herein according to the presentation of the statement of the problems. This study determines the availment and enhancement of benefits for senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite.

Demographic Profile

This part presents the demographic profiles of the respondents including their age, civil status, family income, educational attainment, religion, and sources of information.

A. Age

Table 5 shows the frequency distribution of age among the senior citizens. It is properly discussed based on the frequency distribution and its equivalent percentage based on the given age bracket.

Table 5. *Frequency distribution of the age of senior citizens*

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
60-65 years old	59	39
66-70 years old	32	22
71-75 years old	21	14
76-80 years old	18	12
81 years old and above	20	13
Total	150	100

The above table reveals that most of the senior citizens respondents, comprising 39 percent, fall within the age range of 60 to 65 years old, with 59 respondents. The other portion, 22 percent, has an age range of 66 to 70 years old, equivalent to 32 respondents; 14 percent has an age range of 71 to 75 years old, equivalent to 21 respondents; 13 percent has an age range of 81 years old and above, equivalent to 20 respondents; and lastly, 12 percent has an age range of 76 years old to 80 years

old, equivalent to 18 respondents.

Table 6 shows the frequency distribution of age among the guardians of the senior citizens. It is properly discussed based on the frequency distribution and its equivalent percentage based on the given age bracket.

Table 6. *Frequency distribution of the age of the guardians of the senior citizens*

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
18-20 years old	50	33
21-23 years old	35	23
24-26 years old	21	14
27-29 years old	3	2
30 years old and above	41	27
Total	150	100

The above table reveals that most of the guardians of the senior citizens respondents, comprising 33 percent, fall within the age range of 18 to 20 years old, with 50 respondents. The other portion, 27 percent, has an age range above 30 years old, equivalent to 41 respondents; 23 percent has an age range of 21 to 23 years old, equivalent to 35 respondents; 14 percent has an age range of 24 to 26 years old; and lastly, 2 percent each has an age range below 27 years old to 29 years old, equivalent to 3 respondents each.

Table 7 shows the frequency distribution of age among the five (5) personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of Alfonso, Cavite. It is properly discussed based on the frequency distribution and its equivalent percentage based on the given age bracket.

Table 7. *Frequency distribution of the age of the OSCA personnels*

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
30-35 years old	1	20
36-40 years old	0	0
41-45 years old	3	60
46-50 years old	0	0
51 years old and above	1	20
Total	5	100

The above table reveals that most of the OSCA personnels respondents, comprising 60 percent, fall within the age range of 41 to 45 years old, with 3 respondents. The other portion, each 20 percent, has an age range of 30 to 35 years old and above 51 years old, equivalent to 1 respondent each.

Table 9. *Frequency distribution of the sex of the guardians of the senior citizens*

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	78	52
Female	72	48
Total	150	100

In this regard, a close relationship can foster trust and understanding, leading to better care. The guardian should be in good health and have the mental capacity to handle the responsibilities of guardianship. It is supported by the Gerontological Society of America (2023). The ability of a guardian to provide senior citizen care might be significantly affected by their age. Although there fails to be a set age limit for guardians, younger people could have difficulties because they don't have as much life experience and might not be as financially secure. However, older guardians are more likely to have the means and support necessary to give appropriate care, as well as a greater grasp of the aging process.

B. Sex

Table 8 shows the frequency distribution of sex among the senior citizens. It is properly discussed based on the frequency distribution and its equivalent percentage based on the given categories.

Table 8. *Frequency distribution of the sex of senior citizens*

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	71	47
Female	79	53
Total	150	100

The above table reveals that most of the senior citizens respondents, comprising 53 percent, are female, equivalent to 79 respondents, and the 47 percent are male, equivalent to 71 respondents.

Table 9 shows the frequency distribution of sex among the guardians of the senior citizens. It is properly discussed based on the frequency distribution and its equivalent percentage based on the given categories.

The above table reveals that most of the guardians of the senior citizens respondents, comprising 52 percent, are male, equivalent to 78 respondents; and the 48 percent are female, equivalent to 72 respondents.

Table 10 shows the frequency distribution of sex among the five (5) personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of Alfonso, Cavite. It is properly discussed based on the frequency distribution and its equivalent percentage based on the given categories.

Table 10. *Frequency distribution of the sex of the OSCA personnels*

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	1	20
Female	4	80
Total	5	100

The above table reveals that most of the OSCA personnels respondents, comprising 80 percent, are female, equivalent to 4 respondents; and the 20 percent are male, equivalent to 1 respondent.

In summary, table 11 demonstrated a summary of the overall sex of all respondents, the combinations of hundred fifty (150) senior citizens, one hundred fifty (150) guardians of the senior citizens, and five (5) personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of Alfonso, Cavite.

Table 11. *Overall frequency distribution of the sex of the respondents*

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	150	49
Female	155	51
Total	305	100

The above table reveals that most of the respondents, comprising 51 percent, are female, equivalent to 155 respondents; and the 49 percent are male, equivalent to 150 respondents.

In addition, globally, as the population gets older, so does the need for services catered to their individual requirements. Age plays a major impact in defining the services that older persons need, but sex also plays a crucial role. Age-related changes in hormone levels, biological variations, and social norms can all have an impact on an older person's health, happiness, and experiences. This study will look at how gender affects senior citizen care delivery, emphasizing the value of inclusive and gender-sensitive methods.

C. Length of residency

Table 12 shows the frequency distribution of the length of residency among the senior citizens. It is properly discussed based on the frequency distribution and its equivalent percentage based on the given categories.

Table 12. *Frequency distribution of length of residency of the senior citizens*

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
5-7 years	7	5
8-10 years	10	7
11-13 years	9	6
14-16 years	16	11
17-20 years	12	8
21 years and above	96	64
Total	150	100

The above table reveals that most of the senior citizens respondents, comprising 64 percent, fall within the length of residency of 21 years and above, with 96 respondents. The other portion, 11 percent, has a length of residency of 14 to 16 years, equivalent to 16 respondents; 8 percent under 17 to 20 years, equivalent to 12 respondents; 7 percent under 8 to 10 years, equivalent to 10 respondents; 6 percent under 11 to 13 years, equivalent to 9 respondents; and lastly, 5 percent under 5 to 7 years, equivalent to 7 respondents.

Table 13 shows the frequency distribution of the length of residency among the guardians of the senior citizens. It is properly discussed based on the frequency distribution and its equivalent percentage based on the given categories.

Table 13. *Frequency distribution of length of residency of the guardians of the senior citizens*

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
5-7 years	6	4
8-10 years	2	1
11-13 years	9	6
14-16 years	7	5
17-20 years	45	30
21 years and above	81	54
Total	150	100

The above table reveals that most of the guardians of the senior citizens respondents, comprising 54 percent, fall within the length of residency of 21 years and above, with 81 respondents. The other portion, 30 percent, has a length of residency of 17 to 20 years, equivalent to 45 respondents; 6 percent under 11 to 13 years, equivalent to 9 respondents; 5 percent under 14 to 16 years, equivalent to 7 respondents; 4 percent under 5 to 7 years, equivalent to 6 respondents; and lastly, 1 percent under 8 to 10 years, equivalent to 2 respondents.

Table 14 shows the frequency distribution of the length of residency among the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of Alfonso, Cavite. It is properly discussed based on the frequency distribution and its equivalent percentage based on the given categories.

Table 14. *Frequency distribution of length of residency of the OSCA personnels*

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
5-7 years	0	0
8-10 years	0	0
11-13 years	0	0
14-16 years	0	0
17-20 years	1	20
21 years and above	4	80
Total	5	100

The above table reveals that most of the OSCA personnels respondents, comprising 80 percent, fall within the length of residency of 21 years and above, with 4 respondents then the other portion, 20 percent, has a length of residency of 17 to 20 years, equivalent to only 1 respondent.

In summary, table 15 demonstrated a summary of the overall length of residency of all respondents, the combinations of hundred fifty (150) senior citizens, one hundred fifty (150) guardians of the senior citizens, and five (5) personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of Alfonso, Cavite.

Table 15. Overall frequency distribution of length of residency of the respondents

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
5-7 years	13	4
8-10 years	12	4
11-13 years	18	6
14-16 years	23	8
17-20 years	58	19
21 years and above	181	59
Total	305	100

The above table reveals that most of the respondents, comprising 59 percent, fall within the length of residency of 21 years and above, with 181 respondents; the other portion, 19 percent, has a length of residency of 17 to 20 years, equivalent to 58 respondents; 8 percent under 14 to 16 years, equivalent to 23 respondents; 6 percent under 11 to 13 years, equivalent to 18 respondents; and both 4 percent under 5 to 7 years and 8 to 10 years.

The duration of their presence heavily influences the eligibility and scope of benefits offered to senior people in the Philippines. The Social Pension Program is one of the senior citizen initiatives that offers impoverished seniors a monthly stipend. To qualify, individuals must have been residents of a specific locality for at least six months. The Philippine Health Insurance Corporation (PhilHealth) offers Medicare benefits to senior citizens. While membership is generally compulsory, residency requirements may vary depending on specific programs and benefits. Other benefits, such as housing assistance, educational discounts, and transportation subsidies, may also have residency requirements. Seniors who have resided longer in a community often have established relationships with healthcare providers, which can facilitate better access to care (Hoffman et al., 2019). Research indicates that new residents may face challenges in navigating local healthcare systems, resulting in delayed care (Davis & Leutz, 2020). It is also evident that long-term residents are often more engaged in community activities, which can enhance their access to services through social networks (Putnam, 2000).

Availment of Services by Senior Citizens

This part presents how the respondents avail themselves of the following services provided by the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite. It is properly assessed from different areas, particularly the medicine and drug purchases, medical and essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment. The table presents the mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation per group of respondents.

A. Medicine and drug purchases

Table 16 demonstrates a measurement of the central tendency and variability of the given ten statements for assessing the availability of services by senior citizens in terms of medicine and drug purchases.

Table 16. Measurement of the central tendency and variability of medicine and drug purchases

STATEMENT	SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	GUARDIANS OF SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	OSCA PERSONNELS	VI
	MEAN & STD DEV.		MEAN & STD DEV		MEAN & STD DEV	
1. Senior Citizens receive a 20% discount and VAT exemption on generic medicines	3.59± 0.58	SA	3.58± 0.58	SA	3.80± 0.45	SA
2. Senior Citizens receive 20% discount and VAT exemption on branded medicines.	3.48± 0.57	SA	3.48± 0.58	SA	3.80± 0.45	SA
3. Senior Citizens receive 20% discount and VAT exemption on influenza and pneumococcal vaccines.	3.46± 0.58	SA	3.39± 0.74	SA	3.80± 0.45	SA
4. Senior Citizens receive 20% discount and VAT exemption on vitamins and supplements.	3.52± 0.62	SA	3.43± 0.72	SA	3.20± 1.10	A
5. Senior Citizens are informed of the transparency of guidelines concerning the discount and VAT exemption on the purchase of medicine and drugs.	3.46± 0.67	SA	3.30± 0.68	SA	3.40± 0.89	SA
6. There are accessible establishments or pharmacies that recognize the senior citizen discount and VAT exemption for medicine and drug purchases.	3.47± 0.66	SA	3.50± 0.52	SA	3.80± 0.45	SA
7. In our town, there are offers of discounts and exemptions on medicine and drugs for senior citizens that stretch their budgets, potentially reducing financial strain in other areas of their lives.	3.46± 0.67	SA	3.41± 0.56	SA	3.40± 0.89	SA
8. There are only types of medicines and drugs covered by discount and VAT exemption for senior citizens.	2.93± 0.91	A	2.88± 0.80	A	3.40± 0.89	SA
9. There is a systematic process of availing discounts in purchasing medicine and drugs for senior citizens.	3.51± 0.64	SA	3.22± 0.60	A	3.80± 0.45	SA
10. Senior citizens greatly improve their health by taking advantage of discounted medicines and drug purchases.	3.34± 0.86	SA	3.14±0. 79	A	3.20± 0.84	A
OVERALL	3.42± 0.68	SA	3.33± 0.66	SA	3.56± 0.69	SA

Legend:
3.25 - 4.00 – Strongly Agree
2.50 – 3.24 - Agree

1.75 – 2.49 - Disagree
1.00 - 1.74 – Strongly Disagree

The table above displays mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation per group of respondents in terms of medicine and drug purchases. First, the senior citizens have an overall mean score of 3.42 (SD = 0.68), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that among all statements, only statement eight received the interpretation of agree with the mean score of 2.93 (SD = 0.91). Second, the guardians of the senior citizens respondents had an overall mean score of 3.33 (SD = 0.66), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that among all statements, statements eight, nine, and ten received the interpretation of agree, then statement eight received the lowest mean score of 2.88 (SD = 0.80). Lastly, the OSCA personnel respondents had an overall mean score of 3.56 (SD = 0.69), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that among all statements, only statements four and ten received the interpretation of agree; they both received a mean score of 3.20.

In relation to that, it reveals that under the medicine and drug purchases, the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest response rate, followed by the senior citizens, then their guardians. It is visible that even with differences in results, they still have a commonality of agreement with the statement about the way the senior citizens avail services in the municipality.

Elderly individuals frequently encounter distinct obstacles in the realms of medication acquisition and procurement. Such obstacles may encompass physical disabilities, cognitive deterioration, economic limitations, and intricate pharmaceutical schedules. This literature review examines the prevailing scholarship concerning the determinants affecting the purchase of pharmaceuticals among elderly populations, emphasizing the identification of patterns, impediments, and possible remedial strategies. Also, we can consider that poverty remains a significant barrier to a secure retirement globally, which is why many elderly have no access to medicine and drug purchases. According to the United Nations (1998) in the UN Development Program, only a small percentage of people aged 60 or older have any form of income security. Many elderly individuals, especially in developing countries, continue to work well into their later years to supplement their meager incomes.

B. Medical and dental services

Table 17 demonstrates a measurement of the central tendency and variability of the given ten statements for assessing the availability of services by senior citizens in terms of medical and dental services.

Table 17. Measurement of the central tendency and variability of medical and dental services

STATEMENT	SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	GUARDIANS OF SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	OSCA PERSONNELS	VI
	MEAN & STD DEV.		MEAN & STD DEV		MEAN & STD DEV	
1. Senior Citizens receive a 20% discount and VAT exemption on medical services, particularly in terms of diagnostic tests (e.g., X-ray, MRI, CT scan, ultrasound and more).	3.32± 0.67	SA	3.37± 0.63	SA	3.80± 0.45	SA
2. Senior Citizens receive a 20% discounts and VAT exemption on the medical services particularly in terms of laboratory test (e.g., blood test, urine test, stool test, genetic test and more).	3.41± 0.69	SA	3.38± 0.63	SA	3.60± 0.89	SA
3. Senior Citizens receive a 20% discounts and VAT exemption on the dental services particularly in terms of diagnostic test (e.g., clinical examination, x-rays, transillumination and more).	3.36± 0.71	SA	3.32± 0.63	SA	3.60± 0.55	SA
4. Senior Citizens receive a 20% discounts and VAT exemption on the dental services particularly in terms of laboratory test (e.g., blood test, bacterial culture and sensitivity, salivary test and more).	3.29± 0.75	SA	3.28± 0.67	SA	3.80± 0.45	SA
5. Senior Citizens receive updates on medical and dental services offered by the local government unit.	3.27± 0.80	SA	3.26± 0.73	SA	3.60± 0.55	SA
6. Senior citizens are informed about the type of service provided to patients when availing of the discounts and VAT exemptions on medical and dental services.	3.23± 0.79	A	3.27± 0.63	SA	3.80± 0.45	SA
7. Senior Citizens have accessibility to facilities that recognize the senior citizen discounts and VAT exemptions program for medical and dental services.	3.36± 0.66	SA	3.34± 0.67	SA	3.60± 0.55	SA
8. Senior citizens receive financial assistance for medical and dental services from the local government unit.	2.98± 0.98	A	3.14± 0.73	A	3.40± 0.55	SA
9. Senior Citizens know the process of availing the discount	3.16± 0.83	A	3.14± 0.66	A	3.60± 0.55	SA

and VAT exemption on medical and dental services.						
10. Senior citizens have the regular assistance on medical and dental services yearly.	2.94± 0.93	A	3.11± 0.74	A	2.80± 0.84	A
OVERALL	3.23± 0.78	A	3.26± 0.67	SA	3.56± 0.58	SA

Legend:

3.25 - 4.00 – Strongly Agree

2.50 – 3.24 - Agree

1.75 – 2.49 - Disagree

1.00 - 1.74 – Strongly Disagree

The table above displays mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation per group of respondents in terms of medical and dental services. First, the senior citizens have an overall mean score of 3.23 (SD = 0.78), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that among all statements, statements six, eight, nine, and ten received the interpretation of agree, then statement ten received the lowest mean score of 2.94 (SD = 0.93). Second, the guardians of the senior citizens respondents had an overall mean score of 3.26 (SD = 0.67), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that among all statements, statements eight, nine, and ten received the interpretation of agree, then statement ten received the lowest mean score of 3.11 (SD = 0.74). Lastly, the OSCA personnel respondents had an overall mean score of 3.56 (SD = 0.58), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that among all statements, only statements ten received the interpretation of agree, with an overall mean score of 2.80 (SD = 0.84).

Then it reveals that under the medical and dental services, the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest response rate, followed by the senior citizens, then their guardians. Despite variations in the data, a general agreement existed among respondents regarding the way senior citizens residents access municipal services.

In pre-colonial Philippines, the elderly were highly respected for their wisdom and experience. They played a crucial role in preserving and transmitting cultural heritage to younger generations. Their contributions to the development of institutions like government, family, education, and religion were invaluable. However, they are not excuse to significant concerns. Many elderly Filipinos has no access to medical and dental services due to social conditions. As awareness of the needs and challenges faced by the elderly increases, there is a growing demand for effective policies and legislation to support their well-being.

In addition, despite the challenges encounter, the Senior Citizens Act emphasizes the importance of a national identification card for elderly individuals to access the benefits and privileges offered under the law. By which it is mentioned that free medical

and dental services in government establishment anywhere in the country, subject to guidelines to be issued by the Department of Health (DOH), Government Service Insurance System (GSIS), and Social Security System (SSS). The term 'free' means that senior citizens will receive medical and dental services at no cost, provided that the necessary facilities and expertise are available. Medical services include health examinations, medical procedures within the capabilities of government health facilities, and laboratory tests. Dental services include oral examinations, fillings, extractions, and gum treatment.

C. Essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment

Table 18 demonstrates a measurement of the central tendency and variability of the given ten statements for assessing the availability of services by senior citizens in terms of essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment.

Table 18. *Measurement of the central tendency and variability of essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment*

STATEMENT	SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	GUARDIANS OF SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	OSCA PERSONNELS	VI
	MEAN & STD DEV.		MEAN & STD DEV		MEAN & STD DEV	
1. There are enough discounts and VAT exemptions on medical supplies, accessories, and equipment purchases for senior citizens.	3.39± 0.65	SA	3.16± 0.70	A	3.60± 0.55	SA
2. There are enough updates to guidelines regarding medical supplies, accessories, and equipment eligible for discounts and VAT exemptions for senior citizens.	3.20± 0.74	A	3.02± 0.72	A	3.20± 0.45	A
3. Transparent guidelines concerning discounts and VAT exemptions on the purchase of essential medical supplies and equipment for senior citizens.	3.13± 0.74	A	3.18± 0.66	A	3.20± 0.45	A
4. The senior citizens are informed of the guidelines concerning discounts and VAT exemptions on the purchase of essential medical supplies and equipment for senior citizens.	3.26± 0.66	SA	3.12± 0.67	A	3.60± 0.89	SA
5. There is a transparent breakdown of the price and costs of medical supplies, accessories, and equipment before and after the discount and VAT exemption application in the municipality.	3.16± 0.76	A	3.09± 0.74	A	3.40± 0.55	SA

6. Good customer service or assistance provided in availing the discounts and VAT exemptions on medical supplies, accessories, and equipment purchases for senior citizens	3.32± 0.67	SA	3.26± 0.68	SA	3.60± 0.55	SA
7. Accessible pharmacies and similar establishments that recognize the discounts and VAT exemptions for medical supplies, accessories, and equipment purchases for senior citizens.	3.37± 0.64	SA	3.31± 0.63	SA	3.60± 0.55	SA
8. Speedy and easy availing of discounts and VAT exemption in medical supplies, accessories, and equipment purchases to establishments in the town.	3.36± 0.64	SA	3.20± 0.71	A	3.80± 0.45	SA
9. Inclusion of expensive medical supplies, accessories, and equipment needed by senior citizens.	3.17± 0.81	A	3.07± 0.68	A	3.60± 0.55	SA
10. Great service of discounted medical supplies, accessories, and equipment to overall health conditions offered by our municipality.	3.27± 0.75	SA	3.20± 0.67	A	3.20± 0.84	A
OVERALL	3.26± 0.71	SA	3.16± 0.69	A	3.48± 0.58	SA

Legend:

- 3.25 - 4.00 – Strongly Agree
- 2.50 – 3.24 - Agree
- 1.75 – 2.49 - Disagree
- 1.00 - 1.74 – Strongly Disagree

The table above displays mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation per group of respondents in terms of essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment. First, the senior citizens have an overall mean score of 3.26 (SD = 0.71), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that among all statements, statements two, three, five, and nine received the interpretation of agree, then statement ten received the lowest mean score of 3.13 (SD = 0.74). Second, the guardians of the senior citizens respondents had an overall mean score of 3.16 (SD = 0.69), indicating that the respondents are satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as agree. It reveals that most of the statements received the interpretation of agree, particularly statements one, two, three, four, five, eight, nine, and ten; statement two received the lowest mean score of 3.02 (SD = 0.72). Lastly, the OSCA personnel respondents had an overall mean score of 3.48 (SD = 0.58), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that among all statements, statements two, three, and ten received the interpretation of agree, with all having the same mean score of 3.20.

Then it reveals that under the essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment, the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest response rate, followed by the senior citizens, then their guardians. It is evident in the result that there are differences in the way they agree. Even though the results were not consistent, there was a consensus about senior citizens' use of municipal services.

Moreover, in the 1980s, international research initiatives were undertaken to study the aging population in the Western Pacific region. The World Health Organization (WHO) sponsored a comparative study involving the Philippines, Fiji, Malaysia, and the Republic of Korea, examining the health and economic status of individuals aged 60 and over. Subsequently, the Australian Government's ASEAN Population Program funded a similar study focusing on the socioeconomic consequences of aging in five ASEAN countries: Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand. The Philippine component of both studies involved in-depth surveys of older individuals, gathering data on demographics, socioeconomic factors, family relationships, health conditions, and relevant policies. These research efforts provided valuable insights to policymakers and researchers seeking to address the needs and challenges of the aging population in the region (Domingo & Feranil, 1990). Then in the study entitled "Aging in the Philippines: Findings from the 2007 Philippine Study on Aging" by Cruz et al. (2016), in the year preceding the survey, 16% of older Filipinos reported being hospitalized due to illness or accidents. Of those who sought inpatient care, 52% went to public health facilities, while 40% went to private facilities. The hospitalization rate was highest among those aged 80 and older, reaching 21%. For most hospitalized older people (60%), their children were responsible for most of the hospital expenses. However, 25% of older Filipinos paid the bills themselves. Unfortunately, less than half of hospitalized older adults (46%) were able to utilize PhilHealth benefits. Only 15% of older Filipinos had health insurance, with the majority (88%) being enrolled in PhilHealth. The prevalence of health insurance decreased with age, partly due to the relatively recent introduction of Medicare in 1969.

Summary to determine the availment of Services by Senior Citizens

Table 19 demonstrated a measurement of the central tendency and variability of the overall summary table of the mean to assess the overall determination of the availment of services by senior citizens. The table presents the mean, standard deviation, mode, and verbal interpretation. It is properly ranking the mean score of the three groups.

Table 19. *Summary table of availment of services by Senior Citizens*

INDICATORS	SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	GUARDIANS OF SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	OSCA PERSONNELS	VI
	MEAN & STD DEV.		MEAN & STD DEV		MEAN & STD DEV	
Medicine and drug purchases	3.42± 0.68	SA	3.33± 0.66	SA	3.56± 0.69	SA
Medical and dental services	3.23± 0.78	A	3.26± 0.67	SA	3.56± 0.58	SA

Essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment	3.26± 0.71	SA	3.16± 0.69	A	3.48± 0.58	SA
OVERALL	3.30± 0.72	A	3.25± 0.67	SA	3.53± 0.62	SA

Legend:

- 3.25 - 4.00 – Strongly Agree
- 2.50 – 3.24 - Agree
- 1.75 – 2.49 - Disagree
- 1.00 - 1.74 – Strongly Disagree

The table above shows the summary to determine the availment of services by senior citizens. It is evident that in the given three groups, the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest satisfaction in relation to the availment of the services of the senior citizens, with a mean score of 3.53 (SD = 0.62), followed by senior citizens with a mean score of 3.30 (SD = 0.72), and lastly, the guardians of senior citizens, with a mean score of 3.25 (SD = 0.67). Overall, it is interpreted that there is a visible difference between the responses of the three groups.

Possible Enhancements of Benefits for Senior Citizens

This part presents possible enhancements to benefits for respondents among the various agencies in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite. It is properly assessed from different areas, particularly the hospitals/clinics, groceries, and drugstores. The table presents the mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation per group of respondents.

A. Hospitals and clinics

Table 20 demonstrates a measurement of the central tendency and variability of the given five statements for possible enhancements to benefits for senior citizens in terms of hospitals / clinics.

Table 20. Measurement of the central tendency and variability of possible enhancements and hospitals and clinics

STATEMENT	SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	GUARDIANS OF SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	OSCA PERSONNELS	VI
	MEAN & STD DEV.		MEAN & STD DEV		MEAN & STD DEV	
1. There are enough discounts and VAT exemptions for any services in the hospitals/clinics needed by senior citizens.	3.39± 0.77	SA	3.29± 0.60	SA	3.40± 0.89	SA
2. Good customer service / assistance for senior citizens in the hospitals/clinics provided when availing the discount and VAT exemption on any services.	3.30± 0.68	SA	3.31± 0.59	SA	3.60± 0.55	SA

3. There are transparent guidelines for senior citizens discounts in hospitals and clinics in the scope of Alfonso, Cavite.	3.23± 0.69	A	3.22± 0.67	A	3.60± 0.55	SA
4. Easy and convenient access to the hospitals/clinics that recognize discount and VAT exemption on any services for senior citizens.	3.32± 0.60	SA	3.26± 0.65	SA	3.40± 0.89	SA
5. Easy and convenient claiming of discount in the hospitals / clinics and VAT exemption for senior citizens.	3.33± 0.64	SA	3.24± 0.68	A	3.20± 0.84	A
OVERALL	3.31± 0.68	SA	3.26± 0.64	SA	3.44± 0.74	SA

Legend:

- 3.25 - 4.00 – Strongly Agree
- 2.50 – 3.24 - Agree
- 1.75 – 2.49 - Disagree
- 1.00 - 1.74 – Strongly Disagree

The table above displays mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation per group of respondents in possible enhancements to benefits for senior citizens in terms of hospitals and clinics. First, the senior citizens have an overall mean score of 3.31 (SD = 0.68), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that among all statements, only statement three received the interpretation of agree with the mean score of 3.23 (SD = 0.69). Second, the guardians of the senior citizens respondents had an overall mean score of 3.26 (SD = 0.64), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as agree. It reveals that among all statements, statements three and five received the lowest mean score of 3.22 (SD = 0.67). Lastly, the OSCA personnel respondents had an overall mean score of 3.44 (SD = 0.74), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that among all statements, only statements five received the interpretation of agree with the mean score of 3.20 (SD = 0.84).

Then it reveals that under the category of hospitals and clinics, the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest response rate, followed by the senior citizens, then their guardians. It is evident in the result that there are differences in the way they agree. However, most of the respondents only agree that there are transparent guidelines for senior citizen discounts in hospitals and clinics and easy and convenient claiming of discounts in the hospitals, while most statements received interpretations of strongly agree.

In addition, Cruz et al. (2016) emphasizes that when analyzing the financial burden of hospitalization for older Filipinos, it becomes apparent that a significant portion relied on their children for financial support. For six out of ten hospitalized older adults, their children were the primary source of payment for hospital expenses. However, one in four older Filipinos shouldered the costs themselves. Interestingly, male older adults were

more likely than females to pay for their own hospital bills, with 32% of males compared to 20% of females taking on this responsibility. This trend was particularly noticeable among younger, older adults, where 32% of males self-funded their hospitalization. Despite the availability of PhilHealth benefits, less than half of hospitalized older Filipinos (46%) were able to utilize them. Of those who did avail themselves of PhilHealth, one in five did so as active members, while one in four utilized the benefits as dependents.

B. Groceries

Table 21 demonstrates a measurement of the central tendency and variability of the given five statements for possible enhancements to benefits for senior citizens in terms of groceries.

Table 21. *Measurement of the central tendency and variability of possible enhancements and groceries*

STATEMENT	SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	GUARDIANS OF SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	OSCA PERSONNELS	VI
	MEAN & STD DEV.		MEAN & STD DEV		MEAN & STD DEV	
1. There are enough discounts and VAT exemptions for any services in the groceries needed by senior citizens.	3.03± 0.87	A	3.26± 0.71	SA	3.60± 0.55	SA
2. Good customer service / assistance for senior citizens in the groceries provided when availing the discount and VAT exemption on any services.	3.22± 0.70	A	3.29± 0.69	SA	3.60± 0.55	SA
3. There are transparent guidelines for senior citizens discounts in groceries in the scope of Alfonso, Cavite.	3.03± 0.84	A	3.17± 0.72	A	3.60± 0.55	SA
4. Easy and convenient access to the groceries that recognize discount and VAT exemption on any services for senior citizens.	3.08± 0.80	A	3.26± 0.76	SA	3.80± 0.45	SA
5. Easy and convenient claiming of discount in the groceries and VAT exemption for senior citizens.	3.12± 0.79	A	3.23± 0.75	A	3.80± 0.89	SA
OVERALL	3.10± 0.8	A	3.24± 0.73	A	3.64± 0.74	SA

Legend:

- 3.25 - 4.00 – Strongly Agree
- 2.50 – 3.24 - Agree
- 1.75 – 2.49 - Disagree
- 1.00 - 1.74 – Strongly Disagree

The table above displays mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation per group of respondents in possible enhancements to benefits for senior citizens in terms of

groceries. First, the senior citizens have an overall mean score of 3.10 (SD = 0.8), indicating that the respondents are slightly satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as agree. It reveals that all statements received the same interpretation of agree; statements one and three received the same mean score of 3.03, which serves as the lowest mean. Second, the guardians of the senior citizens respondents had an overall mean score of 3.24 (SD = 0.73), indicating that the respondents are slightly satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as agree. It reveals that among all statements, statements three and five received the interpretation of agree; statement three received the lowest mean score of 3.17 (SD = 0.72). Lastly, the OSCA personnel respondents had an overall mean score of 3.64 (SD = 0.74), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that all statements received the same interpretation; statements one, two, and three received the same mean score of 3.60 (SD = 1.34), serving the lowest mean score.

Then it reveals that under the category of groceries, the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest response rate, followed by the guardians, then the senior citizens. It is evident in the result that there are differences in the way they agree. The senior citizens show agreement in all statements; however, the mean score is lower than the responses of the two other groups. It is properly evident that despite agreement to the statements, particularly on how they may avail services in the groceries, it is still different the way their guardian and the OSCA see it.

In 2010, the Philippine government expanded the benefits available to senior citizens through the Expanded Senior Citizens Act (RA 9994). This law aims to improve the well-being of older adults and recognizes their valuable contributions to society. Key benefits under RA 9994 include discounts on medicine, treatments, professional fees, and basic commodities. The Philippines is one of the few countries worldwide with specific policies and legislation to support older persons. While RA 9994 is a significant step forward, challenges remain in ensuring that senior citizens can fully access and benefit from these entitlements. One area that requires clarification is whether the same discounts apply to vaccines, essential medical supplies, accessories, and equipment (United Nations Population Fund, 2012, Philippine Statistics Authority, 2012). After the enactment of RA 9994, it was officially published in national newspapers. Government agencies issued guidelines to businesses within 30 days to ensure compliance. The Department of Health (DOH) and the Bureau of Food and Drug Administration (BFDA) distributed a memorandum circular to pharmacies and posted it in some establishments. This circular provided information about senior citizen discounts on goods and services. Grocery stores relied on a joint administrative order issued by the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) and the Department of Agriculture (DA) to determine the specific items eligible for discounts. This order was reflected in purchase booklets provided to grocery stores. (Abocejo, Garcia, Inabangan, p. 6120).

C. Drugstores

Table 22 demonstrates a measurement of the central tendency and variability of the given five statements for possible enhancements to benefits for senior citizens in terms of drugstores.

Table 22. *Measurement of the central tendency and variability of possible enhancements and drugstores*

STATEMENT	SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	GUARDIANS OF SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	OSCA PERSONNELS	VI
	MEAN & STD DEV.		MEAN & STD DEV		MEAN & STD DEV	
1. There are enough discounts and VAT exemptions for any services in the drugstores needed by senior citizens.	3.49± 0.66	SA	3.34± 0.66	SA	3.80± 0.45	SA
2. Good customer service / assistance for senior citizens in the drugstores provided when availing the discount and VAT exemption on any services.	3.43± 0.65	SA	3.41± 0.62	SA	3.60± 0.89	SA
3. There are transparent guidelines for senior citizens discounts in drugstores in the scope of Alfonso, Cavite.	3.36± 0.75	SA	3.32± 0.70	SA	3.80± 0.45	SA
4. Easy and convenient access to the drugstores that recognize discount and VAT exemption on any services for senior citizens.	3.42± 0.65	SA	3.36± 0.66	SA	3.60± 0.55	SA
5. Easy and convenient claiming of discount in the drugstores and VAT exemption for senior citizens.	3.46± 0.64	SA	3.37± 0.64	SA	3.40± 0.89	SA
OVERALL	3.43± 0.67	SA	3.36± 0.66	SA	3.64± 0.65	SA

Legend:

- 3.25 - 4.00 – Strongly Agree
- 2.50 – 3.24 - Agree
- 1.75 – 2.49 - Disagree
- 1.00 - 1.74 – Strongly Disagree

The table above displays mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation per group of respondents in possible enhancements to benefits for senior citizens in terms of drugstores. First, the senior citizens have an overall mean score of 3.43 (SD = 0.67), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them

verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that all statements received the same interpretation of strongly agree; statements three received the mean score of 3.36 (SD = 0.75) as the lowest mean. Second, the guardians of the senior citizens respondents had an overall mean score of 3.36 (SD = 0.66), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agree. It reveals that all statements received the same interpretation of strongly agree; statements three received the mean score of 3.32 (SD = 0.70) as the lowest mean. Lastly, the OSCA personnel respondents had an overall mean score of 3.64 (SD = 0.65), indicating that the respondents are very satisfied with the statements and interpret them verbally as strongly agreeing. It reveals that all statements received the same interpretation; statements five received the lowest mean score of 3.40 (SD = 0.89).

The respondents from the Office of Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, had the highest response rate for this category, followed by the guardian of the senior citizens and the senior citizens. All groups interpreted the survey statements, similarly, indicating no significant differences in their understanding.

In support to that, the Expanded Senior Citizens Law provides for free government healthcare services. These include laboratory and diagnostic tests, professional fees, and medical and dental care. Furthermore, senior citizens in the Philippines enjoy a 20% discount on all prescription and over-the-counter medications. Some drugstores may offer additional discounts or loyalty programs, but these can vary. Essential goods for senior citizens include fresh and canned seafood, fruits, vegetables, and all non-essential drugs (GOPRA9994, 2010).

Summary to determine the possible enhancements of benefits for Senior Citizens

Table 23 demonstrated a measurement of the central tendency and variability of the overall summary table of the mean to possible Enhancements of Benefits for Senior Citizens. The table presents the mean, standard deviation, mode, and verbal interpretation. It is properly ranking the mean score of the three groups.

Table 23. Summary table of possible enhancements of benefits for Senior Citizens

INDICATORS	SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	GUARDIANS OF SENIOR CITIZENS	VI	OSCA PERSONNELS	VI
	MEAN & STD DEV.		MEAN & STD DEV		MEAN & STD DEV	
Hospitals and clinics	3.31± 0.68	SA	3.26± 0.64	SA	3.44± 0.74	SA
Groceries	3.10± 0.8	A	3.24± 0.73	A	3.64± 0.74	SA
Drugstores	3.43± 0.67	SA	3.36± 0.66	SA	3.64± 0.65	SA
OVERALL	3.28± 0.72	SA	3.29± 0.68	SA	3.57± 0.71	SA

Legend:
 3.25 - 4.00 – Strongly Agree
 2.50 – 3.24 - Agree
 1.75 – 2.49 - Disagree

The table above shows the summary to determine the possible enhancements of benefits for senior citizens. It is evident that in the given three groups, the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest satisfaction in relation to possible enhancements of benefits for senior citizens, with a mean score of 3.57 (SD = 0.71), followed by the guardian of senior citizens with a mean score of 3.29 (SD = 0.68), and lastly, the senior citizens, with a mean score of 3.28 (SD = 0.72). Overall, it is interpreted that there is a visible difference between the responses of the three groups.

Relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their availment of services

Table 24 presents the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their availment of services. It is properly needed to measure if there is a connection between the age, sex, and length of residency and the availment of services of the senior citizens in the areas of medicine and drug purchases, medical and dental services, and essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment.

Table 24. Relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their availment of services

VARIABLES	STAT ANALYSIS	CORRELATION COEFFICIENT	P-VALUE	DECISION	REMARKS
Demographic Profile Availment of Services	Kendall Tau-b	0.111	0.465	Fail to reject the null hypothesis	Non-Significant

Remarks:

Highly Significant if $p - \text{value} \leq 0.01$

Significant if $p - \text{value} \leq 0.05$ (*reject the hypothesis*)

ns indicates non – significant if $p - \text{value} > 0.05$ (*fail to reject the hypothesis*)

In Table 18, the Kendall tau-b correlation coefficient of 0.111 and p-value of 0.465 suggest a very weak relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their availment of services. It is evident that the relationship between the two variables has a result through Kendall's tau-b of 0.111; this indicates a weak positive correlation between the two variables and is close to zero. There is a slight positive relationship between the two variables. However, this relationship is not strong. While the p-value of 0.465 indicates that the observed correlation could be due to chance. It is much higher than the commonly accepted alpha level of 0.05, further suggesting that the observed correlation is not statistically significant. In other words, there is no strong evidence to suggest that the demographic profile significantly affects the availment of services among the respondents.

In other words, while there is a slight positive correlation between the two variables, it is weak and not statistically significant, suggesting that demographic factors may not play a significant role in availing services of the respondents. This could be due to a variety of factors, such as the nature of the services being offered, the accessibility of these services, or other factors that are not captured in the demographic data.

Significant difference between the responses of the respondents when grouped accordingly

Table 25 presents the significant difference between the responses of the respondents when grouped accordingly. It is properly needed to measure if there are differences in the way the respondents respond in availment of services and possible enhancements to benefits for respondents among the various agencies in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite.

Table 25. Significant difference between the responses of the respondents when grouped accordingly

INDICATORS	CHI-SQUARED (X ²)	DEGREE OF FREEDOM (DF)	P-VALUE	DECISION	REMARKS
Availment of Services	27.35	2	< .001	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant Difference
Possible Enhancements of Benefits	14.93	2	< .001	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant Difference

Remarks:

Highly Significant if p – value ≤ 0.01

Significant if p- value ≤ 0.05 (*reject the hypothesis*)

ns indicates non – significant if p – value > 0.05 (*fail to reject the hypothesis*)

In the availment of services, the results of the Friedman test indicate a significant difference in the responses, with a chi-squared value of 27.35, degrees of freedom (DF) of 2, and a p-value of less than 0.001. A chi-squared value of 27.35 suggests a strong association between the different groups being compared. This indicates that the variation in responses is greater than would be expected by chance. The DF of 2 shows a significant difference between the responses of respondents; it means that there are significant differences between the groups. With degrees of freedom (DF) of 2 for three groups, the results indicate that there are significant differences among the responses related to the availment of services. This DF suggests you're comparing three distinct groups. If the corresponding test statistic (e.g., chi-squared or F-value) and p-value show significance, it means that at least one group's response differs significantly from the others. The overall null hypothesis, which states that there is no difference between the groups, has been rejected. The p-value of < 0.001 indicates that the results are highly statistically significant. In other words, there is a significant difference between the responses of respondents across the various areas of availment of service. Based on

the Friedman test results, it can be concluded that there are significant differences in the responses of respondents when grouped according to the areas of service availment.

In the possible enhancements of benefits, the results of the Friedman test indicate a significant difference in the responses of the, with a chi-squared value of 14.93, degrees of freedom (DF) of 2, and a p-value of less than 0.001. A chi-squared value of 14.93 indicates a strong association between the groups being compared. This suggests that there are substantial differences in the responses across the three groups. When a Friedman test with DF 2 shows a significant difference between the responses of respondents, it means that there are significant differences between the groups. A significant difference in a Friedman test with DF 2 in the context of three groups for Possible Enhancements of Benefits suggests that there are meaningful differences between the responses of respondents across the various groups. When the p-value is less than 0.001, it means that indicating a strong likelihood that the differences between the groups are not due to chance. The p-value of < 0.001 signifies that the differences in responses are statistically significant, with less than a 0.1% chance that these differences arose due to random variation.

Overall, if the p-value is less than 0.001, it suggests that the null hypothesis—that there is no significant difference between the responses of the respondents across the groups—should be rejected. Also, it means that the probability of observing such a result by chance is very small. This indicates that the observed differences in responses are highly statistically significant, meaning that at least one group shows a notably different response compared to the others. Given a p-value less than 0.001, we typically reject the null hypothesis. This means that we have strong evidence to conclude that there is indeed a significant difference between the responses of respondents when grouped accordingly.

Proposed Information Drive Program

Project title: Empowering Seniors: Information for a Better Life

Campaign Goal: To raise awareness about the rights, needs, and contributions of senior citizens, and to promote a more inclusive and compassionate society.

Rationale: Information drive campaigns are essential for senior citizens, acting as a vital link between the older generation and the continually changing world. These campaigns ensure their well-being, security, and active participation in society.

Campaign Activity	Target Audience	Objectives	Strategies	Materials
1. Awareness Campaign	General Public	To enhance public understanding of aging concerns and the requirements	Social media campaigns (e.g., Facebook, Instagram, Twitter)	Posters, infographics, social media graphics, and videos.

		of senior citizens.		
2. Workshop on Senior Citizens	Senior Citizens	To inform senior citizens about their legal rights and entitlements.	Organize workshops and distribute handouts and reference materials on applicable laws and regulations.	Workshop modules, handouts, and guides to legal resources.
3. Health and Wellness Campaign	Youth and Senior Citizens	To enhance the health and well-being of our community through accessible information, essential services, and supportive resources.	Organize health fairs offering free health services	Health screening equipment, brochures, and informative posters.
4. Community Outreach	General Public	To partner with local organizations to support initiatives for senior citizens.	Collaborate with local government units to implement programs and policies for senior citizens.	Partnership agreements and joint project proposals

By implementing effective information drive campaigns, we can empower senior citizens to lead healthier, safer, and more fulfilling lives. These campaigns act as a important bridge, providing the older generation with the knowledge and resources they need to navigate an ever-evolving world. Ensuring their well-being and security, these initiatives foster active participation in society and help senior citizens enjoy a better quality of life.

DISCUSSION

The discoveries of the study are discussed herein according to the presentation of the statement of the problems

1. The demographic profile of the respondents of this study has been determined in different areas, specifically the age, sex, and length of residency. It was properly discussed per group. The respondents are classified and divided into three groups, specifically one hundred fifty (150) senior citizens, one hundred fifty (150) guardians of the senior citizens, and five (5) personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of Alfonso, Cavite. In the context of the age of the respondents, for the senior citizens, it was a frequency distribution of the age of the senior citizens classified from the age range of 60 years old to 81 years old and above; most of them fall within the age range of 60 years old to 65 years old with 59 respondents, and the least is with the age of 76 years old to 80 years with 18 respondents. Then for the guardians of the senior citizens, it was classified from the age range of 18 years old to 30 years old and above; most of them fall within the age range of 18 to 20 years old, with 50 respondents, and the least is with the age of 27 years old to 29 years old, equivalent to 3 respondents each. Then for the five (5) personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of Alfonso, Cavite, it was classified from the age range of 30 years old to 51 years old and above; most of them fall within the age range of 41 years old to 45 years old, with 3 respondents and only 1 respondent from 51 years old and above. Then, from three hundred five (305) total respondents from three groups, it revealed that most of the respondents are female, with 155 respondents, equivalent to 51 percent of the entire population; however, the remaining 150 respondents are male, equivalent to remaining 49 percent. Then for the length of residency, most of the respondents, comprising 181 respondents, fall within the length of residency of 21 years and above in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite.
2. In the availment of services of the senior citizens, it was properly assessed from different areas, particularly the medicine and drug purchases, medical and essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment. In the first area, the medicine and drug purchases, it reveals that the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest agreement with the statement, with a mean score of 3.56 interpreted as "strong agree," followed by the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.42 interpreted as "strong agree," and lastly the guardians of the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.33 interpreted as "strong agree." Despite changes in the mean score, they have all the same interpretations, with an overall mean score of 3.44 interpreted as "strong agree". In the second area, the medical and dental services, it reveals that the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest agreement with the statement, with a mean score of 3.56 interpreted as "strong agree," followed by the guardians of the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.26 interpreted as "strong agree," and lastly the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.23 interpreted as "agree.". It reveals that among the three groups, only the senior citizens have the most

agreement with the statements used in this area. It has an overall score of 3.35, interpreted as "strong agree." Then in the last area, the essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment, it reveals that the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest agreement with the statement, with a mean score of 3.48 interpreted as "strong agree," followed by the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.26 interpreted as "strong agree," and lastly the guardians of the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.16 interpreted as "agree.". It reveals that among the three groups, only the guardian has the agreement to the statements used in this area. It has an overall score of 3.3, interpreted as "strong agree." The data shows that among the three groups, all areas received strong agreements from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA), different from the two other groups with two strong agreements to two areas with only one agreement. Despite the differences in mean scores, they still believe that all statements are correct, and no one received disagreement.

3. In the possible enhancements to benefits for senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, it was properly assessed from various agencies, particularly the hospitals and clinics, groceries, and drugstores. In the first area, the hospitals and clinics, it reveals that the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest agreement with the statement, with a mean score of 3.44 interpreted as "strong agree," followed by the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.31 interpreted as "strong agree," and lastly the guardians of the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.26 interpreted as "strong agree." Despite variations in the mean scores, their interpretations remain consistent, with an overall mean score of 3.34 interpreted as "strong agree". In the second area, the groceries, it reveals that the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest agreement with the statement, with a mean score of 3.64 interpreted as "strong agree," followed by the guardians of the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.24 interpreted as "agree," and lastly the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.10 interpreted as "agree." It reveals that among the three groups, only the senior citizens have the most agreement with the statements used in this area compared to two remaining groups with only agreement with the statement. It has an overall score of 3.33, interpreted as "strong agree." Then in the last area, the drugstores, it reveals that the respondents from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) in Alfonso, Cavite, have the highest agreement with the statement, with a mean score of 3.64 interpreted as "strong agree," followed by the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.43 interpreted as "strong agree," and lastly the guardians of the senior citizens with a mean score of 3.36 interpreted as "strong agree." Despite variations in the mean scores, their interpretations remain consistent, with an overall mean score of 3.48 interpreted as "strong agree". The data indicates that, among the three groups, the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) expressed strong agreement across all areas. In contrast, the other two groups showed strong agreement in only two areas, with one area receiving only a single agreement. Despite the differences in mean scores, all groups maintained that the statements were accurate, with no instances of disagreement reported.

4. One of the objectives of this study was to determine if there is a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents as a combination of all groups, specifically one hundred fifty (150) senior citizens, one hundred fifty (150) guardians of the senior citizens, and five (5) personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of Alfonso, Cavite, and their responses to the availment of services in the areas of medicine and drug purchases, medical and dental services, and essential health medical supplies, accessories, and equipment. Using Kendall tau-b, with a correlation coefficient of 0.111 and p-value of 0.465, it reveals that there is no significant relationship between the two variables. The age, sex, and length of residency of the respondents have no significant relationship with the way they view the availment of services for the senior citizens. The p-value of 0.465 obtained from the analysis using Kendall's Tau-b indicates a lack of significant correlation between the responses of the different groups regarding the availment of services and possible enhancements. The lack of a significant correlation implies that regardless of how respondents are grouped, their responses do not differ markedly. Meaning, the decision failed to reject the null hypothesis.
5. The respondents of the study were divided into three groups, particularly the senior citizens, their guardians, and personnel from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite. Then one of the objectives of this study was to determine if there is a significant difference between the responses of the respondents when grouped accordingly. Using the Friedman test, it was used to compare the means of three groups. In the first indicators, the availment of services indicates a significant difference in the responses, with a chi-squared value of 27.35, degrees of freedom (DF) of 2, and a p-value of less than 0.001. This indicates that the variation in responses is greater than would be expected by chance. Like the second indicator, the possible enhancements of benefits indicate a significant difference in the responses of the, with a chi-squared value of 14.93, degrees of freedom (DF) of 2, and a p-value of less than 0.001. This indicates that there are significant differences in the responses among the three groups. In statistical significance, a low p-value indicates that the differences in responses are unlikely to have occurred by chance. Then, in a variability in responses, the analysis likely showed that the mean scores or rankings of the responses differed noticeably across the groups. Such variability suggests that each group may have unique scores in the statements used in this study. In all given findings, it was collectively supported by the conclusion that there are significant differences in the responses among the three groups.
6. The recommended information campaign that focuses on educating senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, about the services and benefits available to them is properly described more as output explained in the later part. This campaign is elaborated on in the later sections. The findings are derived from the comments and suggestions provided by respondents during the data gathering process, as well as from existing online resources that can be adapted and modified for this study.

Conclusions

Guided by the results of the study, the following conclusions have been formed:

1. It is evident that all the respondents are of legal age. Most of the respondents are considered old, by which the guardian of the senior citizens is with the age above 30 years old and typically belongs to the Millennial generation (born approximately 1981–1996) or Generation X (born approximately 1965–1980). Also, regardless of the age, they all agree that the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, offers good services for the senior citizens. Then, under the category of their length of residency, most of them have 21 years of age and are residents of the said municipality. We can conclude that it is important when evaluating a system in a particular area for several reasons: familiarity with local issues since older residents typically have a deeper understanding of local challenges, needs, and resources, enabling them to provide more informed opinions about the effectiveness of services and systems; and community engagement since those with longer residency are often more engaged in community activities and governance, leading to more active participation in discussions about local services and policies; and also, they may provide more stable and consistent feedback.
2. In examining the availment of services for senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, it is evident that all respondent groups, regardless of their clustering, agree that there is good service available in areas such as medicine and drug purchases, medical and dental services, and essential health supplies, accessories, and equipment for senior citizens. However, the personnel from the Office of Senior Citizens Affairs reported the highest satisfaction rates compared to the senior citizens and their guardians. Notably, the findings indicate that there were no disagreements among the respondents in this category. This consensus suggests a general approval of the services provided, highlighting areas of strength in the system supporting senior citizens.
3. In exploring potential enhancements to benefits for senior citizens, the study reveals that there was no disagreement among the respondents. Regardless of their clustered group, all participants agree that discounts and benefits continue to apply in hospitals and clinics, grocery stores, and drugstores. They also support the availability of additional services, such as access to government healthcare programs, including PhilHealth benefits, and special health services designed for senior citizens. Furthermore, the implementation and enforcement of municipal ordinances were acknowledged as important. However, the respondents did provide some recommendations for enhancement, which are included in the study's recommendations section. These suggestions reflect the collective insights of the respondents and aim to further improve the services and benefits available to senior citizens.
4. The study examines the relationship between the demographic profiles of respondents—specifically their age, sex, and length of residency—and their

responses to the availment of services. The findings indicate that it can conclude that these demographic factors do not significantly relate respondents' responses to the services offered. Regardless of their demographic profiles, respondents consistently recognize that senior citizens receive a 20% discount and VAT exemption on both generic and branded medicines, vitamins, and supplements, as well as medical services, including diagnostic tests. Additionally, there is no discrimination in the provision of benefits and services, irrespective of how long the respondents have lived in the municipality. This analysis underscores that the equitable distribution of these benefits and services is perceived uniformly across different demographic groups, highlighting the inclusivity of the policies in place.

5. The study explores the differences in responses regarding the availment of services and potential enhancements to benefits among various agencies in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite. The findings indicate that significant differences exist in these responses. While all groups generally agree with the statements related to the benefits and services received by senior citizens, a closer examination reveals noteworthy variations in satisfaction levels. Statistical analysis demonstrates that there are differences in the weighted mean scores for specific questions across different agencies, suggesting that some agencies may be more effective than others in delivering services or benefits. Although the majority of senior citizens expressed strong agreement with the statements, some guardians conveyed a more moderate perspective, which highlights a potential disconnect between the two groups. These findings underscore the importance of understanding and addressing the specific needs and expectations of senior citizens. It is essential to identify areas where certain agencies can enhance their performance, particularly in light of the statistical differences identified in this study. By focusing on these areas for improvement, service providers can work towards creating a more effective and satisfying experience for both senior citizens and their guardians, as well as the office, which addresses the needs of the respondents.
6. In the given findings, to enhance the well-being of senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite, an information drive is essential to raise awareness about available services, benefits, and resources. Many may not be aware of the support available to them, so providing clear information is crucial. This initiative should prioritize improving access to healthcare and affordability. Key strategies include expanding Medicare coverage, subsidizing prescription drugs, establishing senior-friendly healthcare facilities, and promoting preventive healthcare measures. In addition to healthcare improvements, increasing financial security for seniors is needed. This can be achieved through indexed social pensions, expanded coverage, financial literacy programs, and support for entrepreneurship. Such measures would empower seniors to manage their finances more effectively and create opportunities for self-sufficiency. Moreover, enhancing housing and living conditions is essential. Providing subsidized housing, offering home modification grants, and developing safe, accessible communities will help seniors live comfortably and securely in their own homes. Fostering social inclusion and overall well-being is also vital. Establishing community centers, volunteer programs, mental health support initiatives, and intergenerational

activities can create vibrant, supportive environments where seniors feel valued and connected. Finally, strengthening advocacy and awareness efforts is imperative. This includes advocating for policy reforms, conducting public awareness campaigns, and empowering senior citizens to be active participants in their communities. By implementing these recommendations, the Municipality of Alfonso can significantly improve the quality of life for its senior citizens, ensuring they live with dignity, health, and security. Such initiatives will not only benefit seniors but will also enrich the community, fostering a more inclusive and supportive environment for all residents.

Recommendations

The data gathered by the researcher through a survey questionnaire were analyzed and interpreted. With the assessed and concluded results, the researcher was able to come up with the following ideas that could be recommended for the enhancement of benefits and services for senior citizens in the Municipality of Alfonso, Cavite.

Guided by the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations have been formed:

1. First, for the public, the researchers recommend utilizing the findings of this study to raise awareness about the additional benefits and privileges available to senior citizens. This knowledge can empower the public to guide senior citizens in accessing the benefits stipulated in the Expanded Senior Citizens Act of 2010.
2. The researchers recommend that the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Alfonso Cavite and healthcare providers align with the Expanded Senior Citizens Act of 2010 to better address the healthcare needs of the elderly. They should enhance transparency and accessibility to healthcare facilities while recognizing the specific support seniors require, ultimately improving satisfaction levels. Additionally, the LGU should disseminate information about the rights and benefits of senior citizens under Republic Act 9994, particularly the 20% discount on goods and services, to raise awareness among establishments and service providers. Also, it is necessary to establish a special desk within the Office of the Senior Citizens (OSCA) dedicated to addressing the challenges and discrepancies senior citizens encounter when claiming their rights and benefits. This empowers senior citizens and prevents feelings of rejection or neglect.
3. To the establishments in the municipality, it is recommended to enhance transparency and awareness by posting visible stickers or banners that inform senior citizens of their eligibility for discounts. This initiative could help remind senior citizens of their rights and potentially reduce complaints. Additionally, grocery stores could adopt a practice of displaying both the regular and discounted prices for eligible items on price checkers. This would provide a clear and convenient way for senior citizens to understand the discounts available to them.

4. Future research could delve deeper into this topic by increasing the sample size, assessing public awareness of existing laws and policies for senior citizens, and expanding the study to include all implementing establishments. Additionally, considering respondents' socio-economic and educational backgrounds may provide valuable insights. To broaden the scope, future studies could involve other relevant institutions like the Municipal Social Welfare and Development (MSWD), Provincial Social Welfare and Development (PSWD), and Federation of Senior Citizens as respondents. Furthermore, incorporating demographic factors such as educational attainment, religion, and language spoken as predictors could enhance the analysis. Also recommending conducting the study in other municipalities and cities in the Province of Cavite and using other research methods, specifically qualitative, to address the in-depth assessment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made sure to follow ethical standards in research through these ways. The participants were given a consent form that the researchers prepared to ensure that no person will be forced to participate in the study if they do not give their consent after the researchers have explained the nature and purpose of the study. The researchers did not require the respondents to give any personal information except for their age, number of years in their place of residence, and whether they are beneficiaries of the Expanded Senior Citizens Act of 2010, as these were required for the study. All the participants willingly confirmed their participation, however, some refused to sign any form. The participants' request not to sign the form was followed by the researchers.

In accordance with Republic Act No. 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the respondents' name, contact information, and other personal information will strictly remain between them and the researchers. The researchers also assured the participants that any information from the interview will not be used, in any forms for any other reasons except as data for this study.

After the data gathering is complete and the study is finished, copy of the paper will not be given to any bodies without proper procedures such as a formal letter requesting for a copy and personally letting the researchers know about the intent to possess a full copy of the paper. This will extend even to personnels of the university, LGUs, other students, etc. Lastly, to ensure the absolute protection of the personal information of the participants, the researchers will ensure that the paper containing personal information be destroyed and discarded after the researchers are sure that the final manuscript for this study is completed.

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